

STRATEGIC INTERVENTION MATERIALS USING LUMI EDUCATION (SIMULE) AND STUDENTS' CONCEPTUAL UNDERSTANDING AND PROCEDURAL FLUENCY

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Strategic Intervention Materials Using Lumi Education (SIMULE) and Students' Conceptual Understanding and Procedural Fluency

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Abstract

In response to the pressing need for innovative educational approaches, this research investigates the implementation of SIMULE to evaluate its impact on the conceptual understanding and procedural fluency of Grade 7 students. This study focused on utilizing SIMULE as an instructional resource in improving the conceptual understanding and procedural fluency of Grade 7 students at Lambayong National High School, School Year 2023 – 2024. A total of 89 students were the respondents of the study. Respondents were selected through purposive sampling and grouped using simple random sampling. This study employed a quasi-experimental design. The data were gathered using the researcher-made pretest and posttest. Mean and standard deviation determined the student's concept fluency level and procedural understanding. T-test was used to determine the significant difference between the two groups' pretest and posttest scores and the mean gain scores. The study revealed that both groups had little mastery of the topics before the conduct of the study. In the posttest, both groups improved their conceptual understanding and procedural fluency. It revealed that using SIMULE and conventional teaching can help students improve their conceptual understanding and procedural fluency. However, students exposed to SIMULE performed better than those exposed to traditional teaching. Further, the learning gains were significantly higher in favor of the students exposed to SIMULE. Thus, the study recommended using SIMULE as an intervention material to improve students' conceptual understanding and procedural fluency.

Keywords: *lumi education, conceptual understanding, procedural fluency*

Introduction

Education was one of the most affected industries when the COVID-19 pandemic struck the country. Education leaders, including school principals and teachers, are developing innovations to facilitate and promote student learning. The education department initiated and crafted the Basic Education (BE)-Learning Continuity Plan (LCP) via Department Order No. 012, Series of 2020, adopting different methods of learning such as virtual schooling, modular learning, and instruction by radio to ensure that education is offered without compromising the health and welfare of learners and school employees.

Based on the survey results conducted before the opening of the school year, the Lambayong National High School adopted the use of self-learning modules (SLMs). After the first two quarters, the researcher found that the students copied the answers on the answer key at the back of every SLM. Moreover, after administering the first two quarterly assessments or periodical exams, it was found that some competencies were not mastered. Sison (2021) affirms that learners struggle to answer mathematics modules because of difficulty in conceptual understanding.

Least-learned competencies in mathematics have been a perennial problem in the Philippine educational arena. According to Dahar (2011), cited by Abuda et al. (2019), most students complain about the difficulty of the subject, and they typically have no interest in learning it. It was found that 70% of the students are not fond of mathematics.

Magsambol (2020) stated that according to the 2019 Trends in the International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS) outcomes, the Philippines remained at the bottom across 58 nations for Grade 4 Maths and Science with a mean score of 297. It revealed that the average is significantly lower than the center point of the TIMSS scale. In terms of the National Achievement Test (NAT) in Mathematics, Saclao (2016) stated that the performance of students in secondary mathematics has not improved in the past decade (NAT 2005–2015). In the division of Sultan Kudarat, the results of the National Achievement Test for Grade 10 showed that the students' problem-solving skills have an MPS of 44.14, and critical thinking has an MPS of 37.38. Thus, there is still a need for improvement in the ratings. With this, the Schools Division Superintendent Fontanilla urged every school leader and teacher to be concerned (Tantawan, 2019).

With that arising issue, teachers in the country are encouraged to create and utilize Strategic Intervention Material (SIM) based on Department Order No. 39, s. 2012, to address the learning gaps among students that were not developed during regular classroom teaching. According to Suarez and Casinillo (2020), SIM aids in re-teaching least-mastered competencies or topics not developed during classroom instruction. It also allows students to delve deeper into understanding the topic and assists them in mastering a competency-based skill (Bunagan, 2012).

Previous studies on the utilization of strategic intervention material only revolved around students' academic performance and learning approaches, solving problems in Math 9, validation and effectiveness of the developed SIM, teachers' perspective, printed SIM, competency-based SIM, conversational SIM using MALMath and DESMOS, using Quick-Response (QR) code, using KOTOBEE,

and with the use of creative games (Salviejo et al., 2014; Dumigsi & Cabrella, 2019; Luzano, 2020; Limbago-Bastida, 2022; Dacumos, 2016; Sison, 2021; Sadsad, 2022; Mercado & Tandog, 2018; Abuda et al., 2019; Uncad, 2022; Balaaldia, 2022). However, no literature has delved into using SIM using Lumi Education in the context of grade 7 nor concentrated on the student's conceptual understanding and procedural fluency in mathematics.

In light of strategies learned by the researcher in a Division Seminar-Workshop on Mathematical Investigation and a seminar on the use of Lumi Education in SLMs to fill the knowledge gaps caused by the pandemic, the researcher chose to assess the influence of utilizing SIM using Lumi Education on students' proficiency in Mathematics which comprises the conceptual understanding and procedural fluency.

Research Questions

This study determined the effect of utilizing the Strategic Intervention Materials Using Lumi Education (SIMULE) as an instructional resource in improving the conceptual understanding and procedural fluency of Grade 7 students at Lambayong National High School (LamNHS), Rang-ay, Poblacion, Lambayong, Sultan Kudarat. It answered the following questions:

1. To what extent is the assessment of the developed SIMULE in terms of:
 - 1.1. content;
 - 1.2. suitability;
 - 1.3. accessibility; and,
 - 1.4. educational quality?
2. What is the level of conceptual understanding and procedural fluency of students in the control group and experimental group in the:
 - 2.1. pretest; and,
 - 2.2. posttest?
3. Is there a significant difference between the students' pretest and posttest scores of the two (2) groups in their:
 - 3.1. conceptual understanding; and,
 - 3.2. procedural fluency?
4. Is there a significant difference between the mean gain scores of the control and experimental groups in their:
 - 4.1. conceptual understanding; and,
 - 4.2. procedural fluency?

Literature Review

Mathematics is frequently considered tedious, difficult, and disagreeable (Omstein, 2002). Effective mathematics education involves discussion over the possibilities and alternatives. Suppose instructors can employ an array of teaching strategies that are personalized to the student's style of learning to bring every educational engagement to life. In that case, this erroneous belief in arithmetic may be dispelled.

Educational materials are tools that aid in the comprehension of a lesson. Educational media involves the learner's senses through sound, a picture, or an array. He characterized it as an instrument that enhances classroom interaction and promotes mutual comprehension between teachers and students. Concerning him, educational materials aim to raise the bar for all students in the classroom. As engaging components, instructional resources can aid teachers of every grade level in providing relevant instruction and encouraging student academic achievement.

Dahar (2011) asserts that instructional materials are paramount in facilitating the teaching and learning process. His research demonstrated that instructional materials significantly influence students' academic achievement; additionally, ensuring that these materials are consistently accessible to students and promote effective learning.

The research results by Adebule and Ayoola (2015) suggested that students taught utilizing instructional materials outperform the control group. In most cases, students' mathematical performance would improve if they were given more opportunities to actively engage with the mathematical curriculum using appropriate instructional materials.

The study of Matlale (2017) and Popoola (2020), cited by Sadsad (2022), emphasized that the use of instructional materials has a significant effect on student academic performance. It is shown that limited and inappropriate instructional materials greatly affect students' academic performance because they connect how students accomplish the tasks given to them.

Some children, particularly those labeled sluggish learners, may require additional mathematics support. Students who excel in a certain field may need further assistance in another. Mathematically struggling students should seek assistance from intervention programs. It is possible when teachers employ an array of tests highlighting every pupil's distinct area of deficiency and then use the resulting data to identify which enrichment lessons will help students better understand mathematical concepts and ideas (Kautzman, 2012).

Interventions can take numerous forms and are highly adaptable. Teachers may accomplish this through classroom instruction, private or group tutoring, or specialized "tiered support" programs. Regardless of the conceptual basis, the focus of an intervention should be

on enhancing learners' understanding by offering them individually tailored instructions through formative knowledge assessments. Remediation has an opportunity to narrow the gap while assisting students' adjustment between courses by improving and developing their fundamental and procedural understanding of mathematics.

Long-term intervention objectives may help students assume responsibility for their education by promoting the development and implementation of individualized success strategies. By emphasizing more general mathematical concepts and their practical applications, this intervention strategy aims to prevent students from viewing fundamental abilities as irrelevant, detached, and fragmented.

All intervention strategies are founded on teachers' knowledge and experience in mathematics and based on evidence-based teaching practices to guarantee students' prior mathematical understanding is built upon over treatment. Instructors' ability to employ a variety of examples and techniques of ordering or categorizing problems assists students and effectively manages their needs, enabling a multifaceted and varied adaptation of the mathematics curriculum. According to Arpilleda (2020), using intervention materials might significantly affect children's academic achievement. He advocated for professional development opportunities for educators to hone their skills in creating intervention materials.

The revised mathematics curriculum for grades K-12 emphasizes exploration as a means to problem-solving and critical thinking. Parents are suggested to engage their children in mathematical activities to foster their mathematical development. Consequently, in Division Memorandum No. 79, S. 2019, the Sultan Kudarat Division initiated a seminar workshop to explore mathematical concepts and create mathematical techniques, use analytical problem-solving abilities, and enhance students' comprehension of mathematical material.

The current school system in the Republic of the Philippines acknowledges intervention resources as an indispensable aid or instrument for enhancing students' academic performance. According to Dacumos (2012), the DepEd initiated steps to improve students' subpar science and arithmetic test scores. Order No. 39, Section 2012 of DepEd requires the application of strategies to reduce achievement disparities. SIM, commonly called Strategic Intervention Material, is an intervention offered to help pupils catch up in their education. It is a form of supplementary learning designed to enhance the knowledge and performance of struggling students. In line with Memorandum Order No. 117, s. 2005 (Abad, 2005), the DepEd conducted a National Seminar on creation during the summer of 2005. This order is a workshop to augment and broaden instructors' taking tests and interpretation skills and provide them with the tools necessary to produce various supplementary and corrective educational materials.

SIM consists of five sections derived from the seminar-workshop that the researcher attended by Divisional Memorandum No. 79, s. 2019. The first section of SIM is the guide card, which contains the chapter or topic the material covers. It presents the larger context, describes the lesson, introduces focus skills, piques the learner's interest, and guides them toward the task(s). The guide card strengthens student interest in SIM. This section may include prerequisite skills according to previous knowledge and a measurable outcome or product that learners must demonstrate or produce. The activity card is the second section of SIM. This card lays out the activities the student must complete as a skill.

The tasks are designed to give students sufficient practice to automatically apply the skill. The activity card contains a variety of activities designed to familiarize the student with the competencies being developed in the kit. The activity card is a record that includes information on an individual's activities and is considered the heart of (SIM). This section also consists of the tasks and exercises for the students, as well as detailed instructions for developing the abilities required in the three domains and explicit principles, several of which are based on real-world scenarios.

The third component is the assessment card, described by Policarpio (2011) as equally important as the first two. Upon fulfilling the activities, the pupil can assess their skill mastery. According to (Sun Star Pampanga, 2017), the assessment result indicates the understanding and abilities that the student may need to improve on or develop further. According to Bautista (2018), assessment cards measure students' learning comprehension.

The card of enrichment is the fourth component of the SIM. It is a supplementary activity or utilization of understanding and abilities for the student to retain the information. This section provides students with practical activities related to the topic. It could include implementations of the subject in everyday life, business, or other technologies. According to Bautista (2018), this card contains tasks that reinforce the lesson's content and make learning meaningful.

The final component of the SIM is a reference card identifying related publications, internet pages, and other electronic and printed resources. Students can utilize this section as a guide to locate pertinent online resources. Additionally, Policarpio (2011) described referencing cards as a collection of sources students may consult for additional reading.

As Dy (2011) described, SIM is utilized in the classroom to boost student engagement and learning. It is well-written and intended to assist those contending with the topic. Those students who require additional assistance with a specific matter receive it following the regular class period. It motivates students to examine the material and strengthen their abilities.

SIM seeks to enhance and broaden the learner's understanding, comprehension, and skills from the practical to the abstract. They were able to assimilate new concepts and expand their comprehension. Moreover, the objective of the instructional content is to assist

students in acquiring competencies skill that learners could not achieve through class discussions (Bunagan, 2012).

Mathematical Proficiency

Parents want their children to excel academically. Numerous parents devote a substantial amount of time to reading orally to their young children. It is among the most beneficial things parents may do to educate their kids. Researchers do not doubt that these exercises assist children in becoming better readers. Reading and mathematical proficiency go in harmony. Parents can grapple with determining how to help their children with mathematical difficulties. In contrast, parents will lend assistance if they understand the fundamentals of today's math instruction and how to approach the concept (Danley, 2002).

According to the book of Kilpatrick et al. (2001), there are five primary components to learning mathematics. The capacity to grasp mathematical concepts, procedures, and connections is known as conceptual understanding. Procedural fluency is adapting to instructions with skill, precision, efficiency, and sensitivity. Strategic competence is creating, expressing, and discovering mathematical answers to problems. Adaptive reasoning describes oneself clearly and supports conclusions with reason and evidence. A productive disposition constantly sees mathematics as logical, worthwhile, and desired, with a belief in one's hard work and ability.

Teaching children to be competent mathematicians is a labor-intensive process, but if all five elements are met, it is beneficial and essential. Students will be more likely to retain knowledge, solve problems, develop optimistic perspectives, and embrace new information (Garg, 2017). Thus, parents should always remember that their child's academic performance is directly related to their ability to engage with the educator who teaches them.

Conceptual Understanding

By Kilpatrick et al. (2001), conceptual understanding is a comprehensive and meaningful understanding of mathematical concepts. Also mentioned is "understanding why" (Baroody, 2003). Rather than simply memorizing facts and procedures, students are more equipped for the real world if they learn to think critically and apply ideas. They have recognized the significance and potential applications of a mathematical issue. Individuals may learn new concepts by drawing comparisons with what they already know despite the logical organization of their knowledge. Conceptual understanding additionally improves memory retention.

If the interconnectedness is understood, memorizing, applying, and recreating information and procedures is simpler. Students who completely comprehend a method are more likely to dismiss it. They examine their memories to ensure they are accurate. They may attempt to explain the procedure to assist them in comprehending it while making any necessary adjustments. Although not always required, conceptual understanding may be derived from a learner's demonstrated capacity to establish connections between various categories of representations and ideas. In most instances, students' comprehension levels surpass their linguistic abilities.

Significant indicators of conceptual understanding include the ability to explain mathematical problems in multiple ways and an appreciation of the significance of various representations. Exploring the mathematical terrain requires comprehending the connections between the numerous illustrations and their similarities and distinctions. The quality, as well as the quantity of connections established by students, influence their conceptual knowledge. Children's conceptual comprehension of counting is related to age and math aptitude (LeFevre et al., 2006), and the connection may be deeper than that between procedural competence and math achievement.

Students can avoid fatal errors, particularly scale errors, by employing conceptual understanding when solving problems. When pupils multiply 9.83 with 7.65 and obtain 75119.5, for example, they may immediately recognize that this is a wrong answer. They comprehend that two numbers below ten multiplied by eight equals eighty since 108 is divisible by eighty. The logical next move would be to question when a decimal point was misplaced. In line with Rittle Johnson and Schneider (2015), quoted by Gilmore et al. (2017), students with superior conceptual understanding are likelier to demonstrate excellent procedural competence. It is because kids with a firm grasp of ideas have a broader spectrum of alternatives accessible to them when it involves ways to solve issues, including conceptually-based shortcuts.

Procedural Fluency

A process adept is a person who can carry out a procedure through comfort, accuracy, and quickness. Understanding when and how to use them effectively is also crucial. It also implies the capacity to perform a task (Baroody, 2003). For example, procedural fluency is critical to mathematics to improve comprehension of place value and rational numbers. It is also useful for comparing various methods of computation. Techniques such as utilizing a calculator or a computer, such as blocks, counters, or pearls, as well as written instructions and conceptual methods for computing probable sums, alternatives, products, or quotients, are included here.

The ability to anticipate the outcomes of a particular operation is linked to procedural fluency. For instance, teaching children how to divide and multiply by hand seems futile because these skills are not as beneficial as they once were. Algorithms for performing computations mentally or on paper are helpful in many mathematically related daily life activities. It is impossible to exaggerate the significance of effective, efficient, and precise computational operations. Through repeated practice, students can increase their accuracy and output while maintaining a high level of fluency.

Lumi Education in the Philippines

Lumi is a no-cost H5P activity editor. Create, distribute, and upload embeddable copies of the tasks to web pages or Canvas utilizing the online/cloud versions of Lumi or the free-to-use, downloadable program. It streamlines the process of creating engaging formative exams for use as knowledge checks in Canvas courses by instructors and instructional designers.

H5P is a library of customizable, browser-based, and freely available online activities. Using the H5P editing tool, educational designers and teachers can create interactive online content such as crossword problems, diagrams, matching tasks, branching scenarios, and hotspot selection tasks, to name a few. However, formerly you needed a paid account and a private server to operate the program to create and update these activities. The new free software Lumi makes it simple to create, modify, and distribute educational materials online.

Lumi is a desktop application that enables the development, editing, and viewing of HTML5 applications (H5P packages). Various quizzes are available, including fill-in-the-blank, multiple-choice questions, and interactive films. Lumi may be used by anybody, regardless of prior programming experience.

Lumi is the only H5P system that does not need a separate LMS (like Moodle) or CMS (like WordPress or Drupal). Using just your computer and an HTML editor, you may create interactive material and then distribute it to your pupils (Rettig, 2020).

Across the nation, LUMI is already being utilized in classrooms. The education department held seminars nationwide to help teachers cope with interactive materials. The divisions of Parañaque, General Trias Cavite, Tacurong City, Sultan Kudarat, as well as other districts around the country were all engaged in the program. Furthermore, research shows that LUMI education may improve students' motivation to succeed in the classroom (Sumandal, 2023).

Synthesis

Effective mathematics education involves using personalized teaching strategies and instructional materials to dispel the belief that math is tedious and difficult. It requires a prompt and precise identification of students' needs in providing additional mathematics support. Thus, interventions should be tailored to individual students.

Proficiency in mathematics is crucial for performing basic tasks and is essential for success in education, work, and daily life. Conceptual understanding in mathematics is vital for students to think critically, apply ideas, and avoid errors. It improves memory retention and allows multiple problem-solving methods, leading to superior procedural competence. However, contemporary mathematical education faces obstacles, and many students struggle academically despite various strategies implemented to improve their math skills.

The DepEd in the Philippines has implemented SIM as a supplementary learning tool to enhance academic performance and help struggling students catch up in their education. The SIM aims to improve students' understanding and bridge any gaps in their mathematical knowledge, ultimately promoting their academic success.

With the current trends in education, the department encourages the different divisions in the country to utilize Lumi Education. Lumi is a free H5P activity editor that allows users to create and distribute interactive content for educational purposes. It is being used in classrooms nationwide and has improved students' motivation to succeed.

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized a Quasi-Experimental Research Design (QERD) that includes the pretest and posttest to determine the effect of the Strategic Intervention Materials using Lumi Education (SIMULE) on the conceptual understanding and procedural fluency of the Grade 7 students. To assess treatments, quasi-experiments do not use randomization (Balaaldia, 2022). It establishes the causal relationship between a given outcome and an intervention (Balala, 2016).

This research design was applied since two (2) groups were being studied—the experimental and control groups. Before the experiment began, the two groups took a pretest. The posttest results were used to compare the learning gains of the two groups. The control group was exposed to conventional teaching or chalk-and-talk methods, while the experimental group was subjected to the newly designed SIMULE. The control group and the experimental group's pretest and posttest findings were utilized to compile, explain, tabulate, and analyze data to give responses to the study questions.

Respondents

The study's respondents were Grade VII (7) Lambayong National High School (LamNaHS) students. These students were officially enrolled for the School Year 2023-2024. Grade VII (7) students were sectioned heterogeneously at the beginning of the school year. General Percentage Average (GPA) from their prior grade level was not considered in the sectioning process, meaning they were grouped randomly.

The respondents were chosen from the ten (10) grade 7 sections whose students had achieved less than 75% of the second quarter's learning outcomes. Topics for the second quarter that were considered least mastered were approximating the measures of quantities, particularly in length, conversion of metric units of length from one unit to another, solving problems involving conversion of metric units of length, evaluation of algebraic expressions for given values of the variables, addition, and subtraction of polynomials, simplifying laws of exponents, multiplication, and division of polynomials, using algebraic methods to find the (a) product of two binomials; (b) square of a binomial, finding the solutions of linear equations in one variable, and solving problems involving equations in one variable (MELC, 2020). The list of the students from these sections is gathered from the school form 1.

Instruments

This study developed and utilized the SIMULE. The researcher utilized this material to enhance student learning. It would enhance the student's performance understanding and fluency in solving problems on the topics classified as least mastered.

The SIMULE was a research instrument that enhanced and aided students' learning. This instrument has five (5) cards: the Guide Card, the Activity Card, the Assessment Card, the Enrichment Card, and the Reference Card. The guide card contains the topic covered by the material. It presents the larger context, describes the lesson, introduces focus skills and learning objectives, and guides the students toward the task(s). It also includes a discussion of the topic. The activity card outlines the activities the student must complete as a skill. The tasks were designed to provide sufficient practice to ensure students can apply the skill automatically. The assessment card contains problems that enable you to assess the state of skill mastery. The assessment result indicates the understanding and abilities that the students may need to improve on or develop further. The enrichment card contains supplementary activity or utilization of understanding and abilities for them to retain the information. It provides them with practical activities related to the topic. It could include the application of the subject in everyday life (Bautista, 2018). The reference card contains the list of all the sources, including books and online sources where the content of this material comes from (Policarpio, 2011). The instrument was validated using a 5-point Likert scale: 5 – Very Evident, 4 – Evident, 3 – Moderately Evident, 2 – Less Evident, and 1 – Not Evident.

The researcher also made a 50-item multiple-choice test to determine the level of the student's conceptual understanding (see Appendix T). On the other hand, the researcher made 10-item questions corresponding to 5 points to determine the students' procedural fluency. The researcher prepared a rubric to ensure the proper scoring of the test. A Table of Specifications (TOS) was made to ensure the proper distribution of the test items. The tool was validated using a 5-point Likert scale: 5 – Excellent, 4 – Very Satisfactory, 3 – Satisfactory, 2 – Fair, and 1 – Poor.

Procedure

The researcher considered the following steps to ensure the success of the implementation and conduct of the study:

The researcher identified the competencies that were least mastered by the students in the second quarter. After determining the least mastered competencies, the researcher developed SIMULE and a researcher-made test, which were validated by five (5) experts in mathematics. After the validation, suggestions and recommendations were carried out and applied to improve the effectiveness of the instruments.

To test the reliability of the researcher-made test, it was administered through a pilot test to the students who had already taken and passed the lessons and were not subject to the study.

After the validity and reliability of the instruments were ensured, the researcher sought approval from Sultan Kudarat State University's Office of the Dean of Graduate Studies. After that, the approval to conduct was obtained from the Schools Division Superintendent's office, where the school belongs, down to the Office of the Principal of Lambayong National High School (LamNaHS). The researcher also asked permission and cooperation from the advisers of the selected respondents.

After approval, the validated researcher-made test was administered a pretest to forty-four (44) students for the experimental group and forty-five (45) students for the control group. The test result was immediately recorded.

After the pretest, it follows the treatment, which uses SIMULE and was applied to the experimental group. In contrast, the control group received conventional teaching.

After the lectures, activities, and treatment series, the researcher administered a posttest to the respondents. In order to discourage the rote memorization of responses, the posttest questions were presented in a different sequence than those on the pretest. The researcher himself was the one who conducted both the pretest and posttest to minimize threats to the instrument's validity. The respondents' scores were gathered and computed to compare the conceptual understanding and procedural fluency of the respondents.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the findings according to the study's research questions. To compare the means and find out the significance between variables, a t-test was utilized using MS Excel.

Assessment of the SIMULE in terms of Content, Suitability, Accessibility, and Educational Quality

This part comprises the different tables on the assessment of the developed Strategic Intervention Materials Using Lumi Education (SIMULE). It includes four tables, Tables 1 to 4, with the essential information on validators' assessment of SIMULE in terms of content, Suitability, Accessibility, and Educational Quality.

Table 1. *Assessment of the SIMULE in terms of Content*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. Objectives are clearly defined and stated for the content.	4.80	0.45	Very Evident
2. Content is aligned with the MELC.	4.80	0.45	Very Evident
3. Learning activities support the objectives.	4.80	0.45	Very Evident
4. Texts are legible and easy to read.	4.80	0.45	Very Evident
5. The directions are specific and understandable.	4.80	0.45	Very Evident
6. The content is in-depth and enhances conceptual understanding and procedural fluency.	4.80	0.45	Very Evident
7. The layout is aesthetically pleasing to the reader.	4.80	0.45	Very Evident
	4.80	0.45	Very Evident

Table 2. *Assessment of the SIMULE in terms of Suitability*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. The learning tasks are related to the expected skills to be developed among students.	4.80	0.45	Very Evident
2. The material allows the teacher and students to develop relevant skills that may apply to other content areas.	4.80	0.45	Very Evident
3. The material is suitable for individual use.	4.80	0.45	Very Evident
4. The method used is suitable for improving the conceptual understanding and procedural fluency of the students.	4.80	0.45	Very Evident
5. The material develops mastery of the lesson.	4.80	0.45	Very Evident
6. The material is interactive and provides different activities suitable for the students.	4.80	0.45	Very Evident
7. The material is suitable for the age of the students.	5.00	0.00	Very Evident
	4.83	0.38	Very Evident

Table 3. *Assessment of the SIMULE in terms of Accessibility*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. The material is durable and easily material stored.	4.60	0.55	Very Evident
2. The does not require internet connectivity.	4.60	0.55	Very Evident
3. The material is easily accessible.	4.40	0.89	Very Evident
4. The material works properly and effectively.	4.80	0.45	Very Evident
5. The material can be used by all students in school.	4.40	0.89	Very Evident
6. The material is easily updated and customizable.	4.60	0.55	Very Evident
7. The material can be accessed by the students without extensive supervision or special assistance.	4.40	0.89	Very Evident
	4.54	0.63	Very Evident

Table 4. *Assessment of the SIMULE in terms of Educational Quality*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. The material contains easily understandable directions for users.	4.80	0.45	Very Evident
2. The material is meaningful and can be easily related to students.	4.80	0.45	Very Evident
3. The strategies and techniques are engaging.	4.80	0.45	Very Evident
4. The material stimulates the students' interest.	4.80	0.45	Very Evident
5. The material is easily asses what the learner has learned.	4.80	0.45	Very Evident
6. The material allows the teacher full access to individual student monitoring of activities.	4.60	0.55	Very Evident
7. Assessment methods are appropriate and suited to the learning objectives.	4.80	0.45	Very Evident
	4.77	0.44	Very Evident

Conceptual Understanding and Procedural Fluency of Students in the Control and Experimental Groups in the Pretest and Posttest

Tables 5 and 6 present students' conceptual understanding and procedural fluency before and after utilizing conventional teaching in the control group and integration of SIMULE in the experimental group.

Table 5. *Level of Conceptual Understanding and Procedural Fluency of Students in the Pretest*

Groups	Variable	Mean	SD	Verbal Description
Control	Conceptual Understanding	72.82	2.62	Did Not Meet Expectations
	Procedural Fluency	71.93	2.26	Did Not Meet Expectations

Experimental	Conceptual Understanding	73.48	4.29	Did Not Meet Expectations
	Procedural Fluency	71.70	1.73	Did Not Meet Expectations

Table 6. Level of Conceptual Understanding and Procedural Fluency of Students in the Posttest

Groups	Variable	Mean	SD	Verbal Description
Control	Conceptual Understanding	83.20	3.92	Satisfactory
	Procedural Fluency	82.20	5.04	Satisfactory
Experimental	Conceptual Understanding	88.93	2.63	Very Satisfactory
	Procedural Fluency	87.52	4.41	Very Satisfactory

T-test Analysis Between the Pretest and Posttest Scores in Conceptual Understanding and Procedural Fluency of the Two Groups

Tables 7 and 8 present the t-test analysis of mean scores between the pretest and posttest of control and experimental groups in conceptual understanding and procedural fluency.

Table 7. Results of the t-test Analysis between the Pretest and Posttest Scores of the Control and Experimental Groups in Conceptual Understanding

Groups	Pretest		Posttest		df	t	p	Interpretation
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD				
Control	72.82	2.62	83.20	3.92	44	27.87	.000	Significant*
Experimental	73.48	4.29	88.93	2.63	43	26.15	.000	Significant*

* $\alpha = .05$ level of significance

Table 8. Results of the t-test Analysis between the Pretest and Posttest Scores of the Control and Experimental Groups in Procedural Fluency

Groups	Pretest		Posttest		df	t	p	Interpretation
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD				
Control	71.93	2.26	82.20	5.04	44	16.35	.000	Significant*
Experimental	71.70	1.73	87.52	4.41	43	27.36	.000	Significant*

* $\alpha = .05$ level of significance

Mean Gain Scores of the Control and Experimental Groups in their Conceptual Understanding and Procedural Fluency

Tables 9 and 10 reveal the t-test result of the mean gain scores of the control and experimental groups in conceptual understanding and procedural fluency.

Table 9. Results of the t-test Analysis between the Mean Gain Scores of the Control and Experimental Groups in Conceptual Understanding

Groups	Mean Gain Scores	SD	df	t	p	Interpretation
Control	10.38	2.50	87	7.30	.000	Significant*
Experimental	15.45	3.92				
Mean Gain Difference	5.07					

* $\alpha = .05$ level of significance

Table 10. Results of the t-test Analysis between the Mean Gain Scores of the Control and Experimental Groups in Procedural Fluency

Groups	Mean Gain Scores	SD	df	t	p	Interpretation
Control	10.27	4.21	87	6.50	.000	Significant*
Experimental	15.82	3.84				
Mean Gain Difference	5.55					

* $\alpha = .05$ level of significance

Assessment of the SIMULE in terms of Content

Table 1 presents the assessment of mathematics experts on the developed SIMULE in terms of content. Statements 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, and 7 obtained a mean of 4.80 (SD = 0.45) and were interpreted as very evident. As revealed, the validators generally assessed the content of the developed SIMULE to be very evident, as shown in the section mean of 4.80 (SD = 0.45). It implies that the objectives of the developed SIMULE were clearly defined and aligned with the MELC.

Moreover, the material texts were legible and easy to read, and the directions were specific and easy to understand. It also connotes that the materials enhance students' conceptual understanding and procedural fluency. Lastly, the layout is aesthetically pleasing to the reader. Thus, the Strategic Intervention Materials created using Lumi Education exhibited high coherence, organization, and comprehensibility in their content.

Lazo (2021) and Comighud (2020) found similar outcomes, showing that the ways of understanding the content of material are crucial because they constitute how the improvement process takes place. It is projected that the student has a good grasp of the topic and can use it to solve problems related to the subject (Sadsad, 2022). The study was corroborated by Andal (2022), who stated that the learning activities' content should be explicit, comprehensible, and follow the present curriculum guide.

Assessment of the SIMULE in terms of Suitability

Table 2 presents the assessment of mathematics experts on the developed SIMULE regarding suitability. The result revealed that statements 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, and 6 resulted in a mean of 4.80 (SD= 0.45), and statement 7 got a mean of 5.00 (SD=0.00). All items obtained a verbal description of very evident.

This section got a mean of 4.83 (SD=0.38) and was interpreted as very evident. The standard deviation implies that the scores of validators were close to the mean. It also implies that the materials were suitable for the age of the students. The learning tasks were related to the expected skills to be developed among students and may also apply to other content areas. The materials were suitable for improving the students' conceptual understanding and procedural fluency because they were interactive and provided different activities suitable for individual use. Therefore, the developed Strategic Intervention Material using Lumi Education suited the learners' needs, interests, and levels.

According to Feliciano (2017), an essential factor to consider is the learning material, which she recommended should be personalized for each student. Saclao (2017) further stated that to accommodate the change in educational approach brought about by COVID-19, it is necessary to recognize that conventional approaches may no longer be as efficient as they once were. Consequently, current learning methods and strategies for student improvement must evolve to meet the demands of competency-based learning strategies.

Khalil and Elkhider (2016) found that appealing, relevant, and engaging problems were necessary for intervention materials to be effective in the classroom.

Assessment of the SIMULE in terms of Accessibility

Table 3 presents the assessment of mathematics experts on the developed SIMULE regarding accessibility. The result revealed that statements 1, 2, and 6 have a mean of 4.60 (SD=0.55). Statements 3, 5, and 7 resulted in a mean of 4.40 (SD=0.89), and statement 4 got a mean of 4.80 (SD = 0.45). It connotes that the material works properly and effectively. It is undeniable because this section garnered a mean of 4.54 (SD = 0.63), interpreted as very evident.

Based on the experts' ratings show that the materials were easily updated and customizable to match the school's resources and were durable and easily stored. Moreover, the materials do not require internet connectivity, which can be utilized by the learners in school without general command or special support. Thus, the developed Strategic Intervention Material using Lumi Education was easily accessible because it is cost-effective and can be used by all students.

In their research on the production and acceptance of digital strategic intervention materials, De Leon and Justo (2023) stress that the developed materials enhance students' academic performance, especially those with low achievement. In addition, it is cost-effective and paperless, contributing to its environmental friendliness and functionality.

Based on his research, Balaaldia (2022) asserted that digital resources may replace traditional textbooks and other printed materials used in the classroom.

Assessment of the SIMULE in terms of Educational Quality

Table 4 presents the assessment of mathematics experts on the developed SIMULE in terms of educational quality. The result revealed that statements 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, and 7 have a mean of 4.80 (SD = 0.45). Statement 6 resulted in a mean of 4.60 (SD = 0.55). All items were interpreted as very evident.

As revealed, the validators generally assessed the educational quality of the to be very evident, as shown by the section mean of 4.77 (SD = 0.44). It implies that the directions of the materials were understandable and meaningful. Further, the standard deviation connotes that the materials' strategies and techniques were engaging, which can stimulate the students' interest. It also revealed that the materials easily assess what the learner has been learning, and the assessments were appropriate and suited to the learning objectives. Hence, the developed SIMULE passed the educational quality because it motivates the learners to think critically and engage in learning activities.

According to Sogunro (2017), educational quality is defined as teaching in a manner that motivates students to actively engage, think critically, and gain valuable knowledge. It stimulates their interest in the subject, encouraging children to seek more information and develop a sense of responsibility for their learning. According to Dahar (2011), there is a strong connection between the efficacy of intervention materials and students' academic achievement. Therefore, the intervention materials are crucial in raising students'

performance in the classroom.

Students' list of least mastered skills decrease when they employ strategic intervention materials (SIMs), particularly when such resources are content-centered and have practical, real-world applications (Escoreal, 2012). Using colorful, easily understood intervention materials improved students' performance because they developed a personal connection to the content (Gultiano, 2012).

Conceptual Understanding and Procedural Fluency of Students in the Control and Experimental Groups in the Pretest and Posttest

It is shown in the table 5 that the mean scores of conceptual understanding in the control and experimental groups were 72.82 (SD = 2.62) and 73.48 (SD = 4.29), respectively. The experimental group performed better on the mean than the control group. On the standard deviation, it implies that the control group had more consistent scores compared to the experimental group.

Meanwhile, the mean scores of procedural fluency in the control and experimental groups were 71.93 (SD = 2.26) and 71.70 (SD = 1.73), respectively (see Appendix R). On the mean, the control group performed better than the experimental group. On the standard deviation, it implies that the experimental group had more consistent scores compared to the control group.

Generally, during the pretest, the conceptual understanding and procedural fluency of control and experimental groups verbally described "Did Not Meet Expectations" and had a very low understanding of concepts leading to more than 75% errors in solving math problems. It also connotes that both groups did not meet the desired competencies. It also entails that the two groups have little mastery of the topics. It confirms that the two groups may have had the same academic preparation level before the study. Thus, both groups were classified as struggling learners and performed poorly in the class.

The results corroborate the study conducted by Mercado and Tandog (2018) and Sison (2021), which indicated that both groups had a limited understanding of the lessons before the experiment and failed the test with a score below 75%. They noted that to improve their learning, they require manipulative materials and additional learning activities that facilitate understanding of the lesson.

The findings of Suarez and Casinillo (2020) are similarly disconcerting. Hence, the intervention material was required to improve the students' academic performance. According to Matlale (2011), insufficient material resources adversely affect students' academic performance.

It is shown in table 6 that the mean scores of conceptual understanding in the control and experimental groups were 83.20 (SD = 3.92) and 88.93 (SD = 2.63), respectively. On average, the experimental group performed better compared to the control group. On the standard deviation, it implies that the experimental group had more consistent scores compared to the control group. It signifies that the students who utilized conventional teaching (control group) performed satisfactorily, and those who utilized the SIMULE (experimental group) performed very satisfactorily.

Meanwhile, the mean scores of procedural fluency in the control and experimental groups were 82.20 (SD = 5.04) and 87.52 (SD = 4.41), respectively (see Appendix R). On average, the experimental group performed better compared to the control group. On the standard deviation, it implies that the experimental group had more consistent scores compared to the control group. It signifies that the students who utilized conventional teaching (control group) performed satisfactorily, and those who utilized the SIMULE (experimental group) performed very satisfactorily.

Generally, it shows that the students in both groups improved their conceptual understanding and procedural fluency after exposure to different teaching strategies.

Consequently, the conceptual understanding and procedural fluency of the students in the experimental group are better than those in the control group. The experimental group has a high understanding of concepts and fluency in solving mathematics problems while the control group has a moderate understanding of concepts and fluency in solving mathematics problems. Hence, the students in the experimental group exposed to SIMULE performed better, as shown in their mean scores, than the students in the control group exposed to conventional teaching.

Students' performance improves when SIM is used, according to Suarez and Casinillo (2020). Results from studies by Diaz and Dio (2017) and Lazaro (2018) show that using a SIM improves students' performance compared to using a conventional textbook.

The result supports the conclusions drawn by De Jesus (2019) who discovered that students into technology become more engaged and focused while studying the subject matter.

T-test Analysis Between the Pretest and Posttest Scores in Conceptual Understanding and Procedural Fluency of the Two Groups

In Table 7, the control group's mean score in the pretest was 72.82 (SD = 2.62), and in the posttest is 83.20 (SD = 3.92). It resulted in a t-computed value of 27.87. Moreover, the p-value is .000, which does not exceed the .05 significance level. It only means that the conceptual understanding of the control group is significantly evident.

Meanwhile, the table also indicated that the mean score of the experimental group in the pretest is 73.48 (SD = 4.29), and in the posttest,

it is 88.93 (SD = 2.63). It resulted in a t-computed value of 26.15. Moreover, the p-value is .000, which does not exceed the .05 significance level. It only means that the conceptual understanding of the experimental group is significantly evident.

Generally, based on the result presented in the table, it signifies that the pretest and posttest scores of control and experimental groups in conceptual understanding have significant differences.

The research conducted by Sison (2021) pointed out the efficacy of SIM as a supplemental learning tool for enhancing students' understanding of concepts. According to Guevara (2016), implementing intervention materials like SIM can potentially enhance students' academic achievement.

In Table 8, the control group's mean score in the pretest was 71.93 (SD = 2.26), and in the posttest was 82.20 (SD = 5.04). It resulted in a t-computed value of 16.35. Moreover, the p-value is .000, which does not exceed the .05 significance level. It only means that the procedural fluency of the control group is significantly evident.

Meanwhile, the table also indicated that the mean score of the experimental group in the pretest was 71.70 (SD = 1.73), and in the posttest was 87.52 (SD = 4.41). It resulted in a t-computed value of 27.36. Moreover, the p-value is .000, which does not exceed the .05 significance level. It only shows that the procedural fluency of the experimental group is significantly evident.

Regarding procedural fluency, the table data shows that the experimental and control groups' pretest and posttest scores vary significantly. The results are corroborated by Dumigsi and Cabrella (2019). They discovered that students' mathematical ability is significantly improved when SIM is used as a remedial tool. Moreover, they emphasize that students who receive access to this intervention content are more likely to have an increase or improvement in their mathematical ability.

According to the findings of Balazo (2021), the implementation of electronic strategic intervention materials in mathematics describes struggling students as having a higher level of achievement. The generalization above is further corroborated by the results revealed by Zhang et al. (2015) regarding the enhancement of students' learning subsequent to their utilization of mathematics applications

Mean Gain Scores of the Control and Experimental Groups in their Conceptual Understanding and Procedural Fluency

Based on the results in table 9, the experimental group has a mean gain score of 15.45 (SD = 3.92), and the control group has a mean gain score of 10.38 (SD = 2.50). The t-computed value equals 7.30. Further, a p-value of .000 does not exceed the .05 significance level. It means there is a significant difference between the mean gain scores of the control and experimental groups in their conceptual understanding.

Conventional teaching, which was utilized in the control group, and Strategic Intervention Materials, using Lumi Education (SIMULE), which was utilized in the experimental group, were both good in improving the students' conceptual understanding.

Consequently, differences existed in the students' learning outcomes. The experimental group exhibited better results than the control group, as evidenced by the mean gain difference of 5.07. It shows that the students in the experimental group enjoyed the activities presented in the developed SIMULE because it is interactive and engaging. Therefore, the utilization of SIMULE was more advantageous for enhancing the students' conceptual understanding, thereby facilitating achievement in subjects categorized as least mastered.

Dumigsi and Cabrella (2019) assert in their study that SIM can elevate students' academic performance in mathematics. Integrating SIM into the instruction of subjects where students have the least mastery fosters the development of mathematical abilities, including conceptual understanding. It supports the development of fundamental mathematical knowledge, abilities, and comprehension and facilitates the transfer of knowledge.

According to Carlson (2005), cited by Balazo (2021), technology also facilitates the engagement of younger minds and learners' understanding. In addition, her research revealed that instruction utilizing electronic SIM is better than conventional instruction. Students' comprehension regarding the least mastered competencies was enhanced by SIM (Abuda et al., 2019).

Based on the results in table 10, the experimental group has a mean gain score of 15.82 (SD = 3.84), and the control group has a mean gain score of 10.27 (SD = 4.21). The t-computed value equals 6.50. Further, a p-value of .000 does not exceed the .05 significance level. It means there is a significant difference between the mean gain scores of the control and experimental groups in their procedural fluency.

It can be gleaned that conventional teaching, utilized in the control group, and Strategic Intervention Materials, using Lumi Education (SIMULE), utilized in the experimental group, were both good in improving the students' procedural fluency.

Consequently, there was still a difference in the learning of the students. The experimental group performed better than the control group, as shown in the difference in mean gain scores of 5.55. It shows that the students in the experimental group were allowed to perform a different set of activities that stimulated their interests and keep engaged in the lessons. Hence, SIMULE is better to use in improving the students' procedural fluency, which leads to the improvement of lessons that were identified as least mastered.

When compared to the traditional approach, Bastida and Bastida (2022) found that using SIM improved students' learning results.

Learning intervention materials improve cognitive, emotional, and verbal learning outcomes (Pedreira, 2015).

The instructional design is improved and students are encouraged to use different resources to achieve an improvement in the learners' performance (Horn, 2011). According to Mercado and Tandog (2018), students who were taught with SIM with integration of technology excelled than those who were taught using the conventional approach.

Conclusion

The assessment of the developed SIMULE regarding content, suitability, accessibility, and educational quality was valid and reliable because it exhibited high coherence and organization through aligning the contents on the MELC. It also suited the learners' needs, interests, and age, motivating them to think critically and engage in learning activities.

The pretest's conceptual understanding and procedural fluency of control and experimental groups did not meet the desired competencies. Both groups have little mastery of topics and most likely have the same level of academic preparation before experimentation. The posttest scores showed that both groups improved their conceptual understanding and procedural fluency. Consequently, the conceptual understanding and procedural fluency of the experimental group were better than the control group. Thus, the students exposed to SIMULE performed better than those exposed to conventional teaching.

Based on the results of the t-test analysis, it signified that the pretest and posttest of the control and experimental groups' conceptual understanding and procedural fluency have significant differences. The student's conceptual understanding and procedural fluency increased after implementing two teaching approaches.

The result of the t-test analysis of the mean gain scores of control and experimental groups signified that conventional teaching and SIMULE improved the students' conceptual understanding and procedural fluency. Consequently, the experimental group exhibited better results compared to the control group. Thus, using SIMULE was more advantageous for enhancing students' conceptual understanding and procedural fluency, thereby facilitating the achievement of competencies identified as least mastered, as shown in the main gain difference.

Teacher-developer may be encouraged to improve the accessibility of the SIMULE which can be used by all the learners in school and accessed by the students without intensive supervision or special assistance.

Teachers may be encouraged to utilize SIMULE as one of the intervention materials to improve students' conceptual understanding and procedural fluency in Mathematics and other subjects.

Department heads of every subject may consolidate all the topics in every quarter and identify topics with the least mastery as the basis for developing a new SIMULE.

To maximize the potential of teachers in creating innovative intervention materials, the principal, master teachers, and department heads must request that the division office of Sultan Kudarat conduct INSET on the development of Strategic Intervention Material utilizing technology such as Lumi Education.

As part of the 21st-century skills, researchers are encouraged to conduct additional studies on using SIMULE in other subject areas to enhance students' critical and creative thinking and problem-solving abilities.

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